

CAUSES AND SECURITY IMPLICATIONS OF ASSASSINATIONS: THE ROLE OF CLOSE PROTECTION IN VIP PROTECTION

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ABSTRACT

It is known that close protection, as a segment of security, primarily has the obligation to provide protection and safety to very important persons who are exposed to major risks such as assassinations, terrorist attacks, kidnappings, etc. The persons endangered by assassins, in most cases, are heads of state, prime ministers, prosecutors, as well as individuals with high popularity, or so-called VIP persons. In Kosovo, as in most other countries, problems caused by criminal groups or certain individuals are under the scrutiny of the responsible security institutions, specifically the State Police.

Today, criminal activity is increasingly expanding, and this highlights the fact that threats against important persons are more evident compared to the past. Therefore, for the Kosovo Police, the protection of personalities, both domestic and international, must be considered the next major challenge. Although the protection of very important persons is not something new, today the need for cooperation between states is increasingly felt in order to find a more efficient security model related to the protection of VIPs.

Methods: In the preparation of this scientific research paper, we applied the following methods: comparative, statistical, analytical, and case studies conducted at different stages from 1999 to the present. Through these methods, we identified and addressed various aspects related to security, particularly the types of risks in relation to the security of very important persons, as well as the measures that should be taken by protection teams and state institutions to prevent those risks.

Keywords: Kosovo, police, causes of assassinations, personalities of very important persons (VIPs), characteristics of bodyguards.

1. INTRODUCTION

“To be a bodyguard means to live someone else’s life and to be ready to sacrifice your own.” (Berisha, 2019: 9).

The security of personalities depends largely on the efficiency of protective escorting, organization, formation, professional preparation, and motivation. The duties related to the protection of very important persons are carried out by several security bodies, each within its own authorizations and responsibilities, and through mutual cooperation between them.

According to the law in force in our country, the tasks related to the security of domestic and international personalities fall under the competence of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, specifically under the competence of the Kosovo Police. Within the latter, the unit for the protection of personalities is responsible for the safety of the persons under protection and for the security of domestic and international personalities.

The importance of protecting very important persons is shown by data indicating that, in the last century, nearly one hundred statesmen around the world, including in Kosovo, have lost their lives due to assassinations, while the number of attempted assassinations is significantly higher than the number actually carried out.

2. BODYGUARDING IN HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE

The history of guarding goes back to the origin of humankind. The basic survival and caring instincts present in every man and woman – to ward off all kinds of threats, dangers and onslaughts, as well as the innate feelings to protect – have been present with all mankind since the earliest times. More precisely, the principles of bodyguarding, to protect and to take care of others who cannot do it for themselves, have been with us since the time of Adam and Eve (Ras, 2012:8).

A brief look at a possible reconstruction of the “history of bodyguarding” will assist the reader in understanding more about this social phenomenon and will also enable him/her to identify trends or patterns regarding bodyguarding. A look into history helps put different pieces of information together so that a more coherent and holistic picture of bodyguarding can be obtained. This, hopefully, will lead to a better and more honest in-depth understanding of personal protection in contemporary society (Ras, 2005:11).

State (public) policing developed because of social needs amongst members of society who required protection. While individuals looked after themselves since ancient times, they later shifted this responsibility to others to act on their behalf. This led to the origin of official police organization and departments. The year 1829 is normally seen as the time when modern organized policing came to the fore. In this year, Sir Robert Peel started the Metropolitan Police in London, England. This protection included the safeguarding of life and property, the enforcement of the law, and the prevention, combating, and investigation of crime (Heerden, 1994:25-26).

Private security existed in Great Britain long before the public police came into existence in 1829 and was also introduced in North America by English settlers long before the era of Peel. The same can be said of bodyguarding. It has existed long before public policing was introduced. Individuals developed a need to be protected and to feel safe, and they later started to employ others to protect them – normally in exchange for a fee or some material benefits. However, sometimes bodyguarding was carried out for political or religious reason as well (Ras, 2012: 9).

Bodyguarding has ancient roots, with specialized protective units documented as early as the Hittite Empire, where the Mesedi served as the king’s personal guards to prevent assassination and ensure his safety (Beckwith, 2009:1). In classical antiquity, the Roman Praetorian Guard functioned as the elite protectors of the emperor from 27 BCE, combining personal security with political influence within the Roman state. Medieval Europe continued this tradition; for example, the English Yeomen of the Guard, established under Henry VII, originally served as active royal bodyguards responsible for the monarch’s safety before later transitioning to ceremonial roles (Hewerdine, 1998:10–12).

3. THE ORIGIN AND DEVELOPMENT OF CLOSE PROTECTION FORCES

Security work for important personalities, specifically bodyguards, has existed since the time of the ancient Romans. Throughout the centuries during which government dynasties ruled, leaders entrusted their personal security to specially selected soldiers who were completely loyal (Ras, 2012:8). Primarily, these were members of regular armies, but history also records hired soldiers who were specifically rewarded with gold and property for such services, provided they lived long enough to enjoy the rewards. Their duty was to prevent any attack against their patrons – even at times when the patrons were at the height of their power and controlled vast territories, such as the Mongols Kublai Khan and Genghis Khan.

The true predecessors of modern bodyguards are now considered to be the Japanese Samurai. The Samurai were divided into free men who worked under contract for an employer and those who were bound hereditarily to their patrons. The word *Samurai* itself means “to serve” or “to protect someone” (Karahasanovic, 2009:22).

From the 7th century BCE to the 5th century CE, the Praetorian Guard was responsible for protecting government officials and members of their families. This unit, known as the Praetorian Cohort, consisted of both infantry and cavalry and accompanied distinguished citizens of the Roman Empire and military leaders such as Caesar, Mark Antony, and Octavian. In Rome, as the king’s laws strengthened his authority and altered the political role of the Senate, senators – like other wealthy individuals – employed a significant number of soldiers as personal bodyguards for their own protection.

The first ruler to establish organized police forces was Augustus Caesar. These forces were structured as guards, with the primary task of protecting against assassins and maintaining a certain level of security in Rome (Ahić, 2009:74).

4. MAIN CAUSES OF ASSASSINATIONS

Assassinations represent deliberate and targeted acts of political violence aimed at influential individuals in order to achieve political, ideological, or social objectives. According to Wilkinson (2006), assassinations frequently occur in contexts marked by political instability, weak state authority, and intense power struggles, where violence is perceived as a viable tool to influence political outcomes. Furthermore, deep social divisions such as ethnic conflict, economic inequality, and ideological polarization contribute significantly to the emergence of assassination attempts. When political leaders are viewed as symbols of oppression or injustice, accumulated social grievances may escalate into targeted violence. Wilkinson emphasizes that these factors, combined with security vulnerabilities, create favorable conditions for assassinations to occur (Wilkinson, 2006: 54–58).

Political assassinations are acts of deliberate violence against high-profile public figures, usually carried out with the explicit intent of influencing political direction, public policy, or social order. These acts are not isolated eruptions of violence but are often embedded in broader social, political, and environmental contexts which shape both motivation and opportunity.

One major cause identified in scholarly literature is social conflict. Social conflict refers to inter-group tensions within a country, often resulting from ethnic, economic, or ideological divisions. As tensions escalate, frustration and hostility can translate into

extreme violence such as assassination attempts, particularly when segments of the population attribute social grievances to the leadership (Yammarino 2018: 457–475). Throughout human history, very few states have been free from assassinations, or at least from attempts to carry out such acts against statesmen. Since ancient times, when the first human groups began to form and leadership positions emerged, there have always been individuals who, for various reasons, sought to replace the leader. As this type of crime continues to occur today – and in fact appears to be increasing – it is important to ask: “Why does this crime persist?”

Regardless of the high level of security maintained by some states, even the most developed countries are not immune to this dangerous form of criminal activity. In most cases, the perpetrators are citizens of the same state in which the act is committed, raising questions about the factors that motivate such behavior. Historical records also show instances in which assassinations were carried out by individuals from other communities or states.

In Kosovo, particularly in the post-war period from 1999 to the present, several cases of assassination have occurred. These cases appear to have been motivated by a variety of factors, including political, economic, psychological, and personal reasons (Shatri, 2002). Thus, certain individuals or groups have continued to use assassination as a tool to release their frustrations, achieve their objectives, or take revenge for harm experienced – whether that harm is real or perceived.

Protective escorting, which provides the physical security of VIPs, has advanced over time, offering greater protection to various individuals. However, it remains unproven that complete, one hundred percent security can be guaranteed to any personality. Advancements in intelligence services, extensive and professional training, and the use of more sophisticated weapons by protective escorts have forced assassins to modify their methodologies. In the modern era, perpetrators attempt to stay one step ahead of security institutions by employing new strategies to accomplish their missions.

To understand why assassinations occur, it is essential to identify the main causes behind such acts and to analyze in detail the factors that drive individuals or certain groups to carry them out (Dani, 2017). In addition to understanding the causes, knowledge of the operational methods used by assassins is equally important. Such knowledge is particularly critical for members of close protection units, who are responsible for safeguarding high-profile individuals.

Previous research on the causes of assassinations, conducted by both local and international scholars, has concluded that six main factors motivate perpetrators:

1. Political causes,
2. Economic causes,
3. Ideological causes,
4. Personal causes,
5. Psychological causes,
6. Contract killings.

The bodies responsible for national security, as well as those tasked with protecting high-profile individuals, despite identifying the motivating factors, cannot always prevent attacks against the persons under their protection. Over the years, and throughout modern history, almost every leader has lived with the awareness that they may be the target of an assassination attempt (Kosovo Police, 2022:2).

In attempts to kill high-profile individuals, assassins have employed nearly every possible method. While close protection services have continuously strengthened their measures to

confront these threats, they have also prompted assassins to develop new methods to bypass protective security (Šuperina, Moratić & Ahić, 2016:91–110).

After 1999, Kosovo was not immune to such incidents. Various high-profile individuals were targeted with sophisticated and modern weapons,

including handguns, long firearms, and different types of explosives, resulting in both injuries and fatalities. The assassinations carried out in Kosovo involved highly specialized methods, and the motives, as confirmed by the responsible institutions, indicate that the majority of these killings were politically, economically, or financially motivated (Berisha, 2019:46).

5. SKILLS, CHARACTERISTICS, AND KNOWLEDGE OF BODYGUARDS IN KOSOVO POLICE

The work of a bodyguard is extremely stressful and demanding; therefore, individuals performing personal protection duties must possess specialized skills and knowledge. In addition to fulfilling the tasks associated with providing security and meeting the protection needs of the person under their care, bodyguards must also consider the evaluations of their employer, the media, and the public. A bodyguard, along with the entire team responsible for the security of the protected person, practically lives the life of their employer and must be available 24 hours a day without interruption (Radenovic, 2003:11). Although the work is dynamic, a significant portion of time is spent waiting. Therefore, maintaining concentration throughout duty is essential, and tasks should not become routine. Routine and lapses in security create opportunities for those from whom VIPs are protected. Unfortunately, some prejudices persist, suggesting that a bodyguard must weigh 120 kg and be at least 2 meters tall in order to provide protection. However, the primary and most important “weapon” of a personal bodyguard is the mind. Effective performance requires proper perception, readiness, vigilance, analytical thinking, and memory. Close protection personnel must be highly motivated and emotionally stable, possess proper etiquette, communicate effectively, and act discreetly and reliably. A bodyguard cannot afford mistakes in their career, as every error could cost the life of the protected individual.

Therefore, it is necessary for bodyguards to continuously train and improve their skills and characteristics to meet these strict criteria. A bodyguard must be in good physical shape, possess sharp vision and hearing, and maintain a professional appearance. They must remain fully concentrated and focused on their duties regardless of fatigue, as bodyguards often work long shifts to ensure 24-hour protection of their clients throughout all daily activities.

Bodyguards must have the ability to recognize potential sources of danger and remain calm and fully focused under pressure. Considering that bodyguards frequently need to cooperate or coordinate protection with other security forces, such as local police or other private security personnel, they must also possess strong interpersonal communication skills. Training for bodyguards includes the use of firearms, hand-to-hand combat skills, tactical driving, and first aid (Berisha, 2013:17). In many bodyguard units, particularly those responsible for protecting heads of state, personnel undergo additional training for specialized duties, such as:

- Close protection of the VIP during movement on foot and in vehicles;
- Protection of the VIP when moving through crowds;

- Searching for explosive devices, understanding safety rules for handling explosives, knowledge of types of explosives, detonators, and general recognition of improvised explosive devices, as well as conducting vehicle and location checks for explosive threats (Lonsdale, 1995:187);
- Searching for surveillance equipment, recognizing electronic monitoring tools, detecting and neutralizing electronic surveillance devices, and following communication protocols (Druzeta, 2016:206);
- “Counter-sniper course”: comprehensive knowledge of sniper rifles, handling of sniper weapons, identifying sniper positions, and techniques for counter-sniper operations;
- Organizing the protection of the VIP in hotel facilities, including tactics and techniques for ensuring safety within a hotel, from room selection to overall protection during the stay;
- Ethics and protocol: official introductions and handshakes during formal meetings, rules for official dinners, appropriate attire and appearance according to protocol, dining etiquette, arrangement of guests at the table, and understanding academic, noble, and diplomatic titles (Verbac, 2002:12).

6. DAILY PLAN OF VIP SECURITY TEAM AND DIVISION OF RESPONSIBILITIES

The workday begins with a meeting led by the team leader responsible for protection. During this meeting, it is necessary to review the planned activities that the client intends to carry out throughout the day. The team leader must develop the protection plan and assign specific duties and responsibilities to each team member (KFOR – Multinational Specialized Unit, 2023:22).

It is also essential to review and develop movement plans for the VIP from their residence to the workplace. Throughout the day, the VIP may travel by car, train, or airplane, attend meetings in restaurants, or participate in public events. After drafting the plan, one or more bodyguards may visit the locations in advance to verify routes, identify roadworks, potential turns, closed paths, and other obstacles. Detailed inspections of the premises where the VIP will be staying are critical, including the security of the building and auxiliary entrances and exits (Moratic & Ahic, 2015:89).

Physical and technical security work for VIPs and facilities in Kosovo and worldwide is carried out by specialized units within the police and military. It is extremely important that the institutions responsible for VIP and facility security operate in close coordination with sectors such as state intelligence, counterintelligence, and counter-terrorist services, whether in the military or police, as a lack of coordination can represent the largest flaw in the VIP security system, potentially leading to fatal consequences.

For example, one of the tasks of the counterintelligence sector within the military and police is to detect any threats to VIP security and report them to the police. Based on this information, preventive measures are implemented, and VIP protection operates by increasing the security level and activating anti-terrorist units to prevent and neutralize threats.

The unit responsible for physical protection within the security service not only protects VIP personalities but also secures the facilities of highly important persons in various situations and for periods of time according to operational needs. Continuous

security is provided for the highest state leaders and the most important institutions of the system, such as the Assembly and the Government.

VIP security is organized using so-called concentric ring systems:

- The first ring consists of immediate and direct protection around the personality or facility. This ring is composed of the most trusted personnel, who are well-trained and highly specialized.
- The second ring of security covers a wider area and is somewhat broader than the first ring. It is usually a mixed system, composed of both police and military forces.
- The third ring is the most important concentric ring and is “invisible”. It represents security in the broadest sense, as this is where intelligence for decision-making is concentrated and no mistakes are permitted.

Practice has shown that at least two levels exist in which special services operate to secure state officials. The first level is regular readiness, during which services, according to their daily plans, secure the most sensitive locations against potential attacks on state leaders. These sensitive points include their residences (houses and apartments), birthplaces, and the routes they travel from home to work. The second level is a special security readiness, activated when information exists regarding real threats to the lives of state leaders and their family members. This level involves the activation of counterintelligence and anti-terrorist sectors within the police, state security services, and the military, to provide full protection for threatened individuals. The first level of security includes personal escorts and the driver in the armored vehicle, whereas the second level establishes special conditions for the VIP’s stay and work. Members of the service responsible for physical protection are required to stay up to date with the latest technical developments in communication equipment, surveillance countermeasures, and related areas. They must also train daily to perfect the skills necessary for their duties, including driving armored vehicles, close-quarters combat (“hand-to-hand”), combat skills adapted to bodyguard duties, and the use of various tools and weapons – from cold weapons to practical shooting with pistols and other automatic firearms (Berisha, 2019:83–84).

7. THE AMBUSH AND ITS RISK ELEMENTS

An ambush is a rapid, violent, and unexpected attack that is extremely difficult to avoid, as it is carefully planned in advance and therefore poses significant challenges to protective teams and escort operations in general. Ambushes are typically initiated from concealed or covered positions, making it difficult to detect the attackers beforehand. The primary objective of the attackers is to remain unnoticed in order to create favorable conditions for executing the attack.

Attackers deliberately select locations suitable for engaging a moving target or one that has temporarily stopped. Consequently, the choice of position is critical, as all actions are conducted from this location. This area is commonly referred to as the *kill zone* (Zone “X”), defined as the area selected by attackers to maximize the concentration of force and the effectiveness of striking the target (Office of Protection Operations, 2015:34).

7.1. Main Elements of an Ambush

Planning: As with any operation requiring careful preparation, attackers initially focus on planning the operation aimed at targeting a VIP. This planning is carried out well in advance, after which the attackers wait for a favorable opportunity to execute their mission.

Positioning: Following detailed planning and analysis, attackers determine the optimal location from which to execute the attack. They carefully select a site that allows them to act without being detected, without obstruction, and without facing a counterattack from the VIP's close protection team or other security personnel.

Initiation: This phase involves the final field preparations after positioning. During this stage, attackers occupy their positions and assess from which direction the attack should be launched and which target will have the highest priority. In some cases, attackers initially target vehicle drivers in order to stop the escort convoy in advance and subsequently strike the main VIP target.

Confirmation: After analyzing the first three elements – planning, positioning, and initiation – the attackers assess whether the necessary conditions for carrying out the attack have been met. Practical experience has shown that in certain situations, when attackers conclude that the required conditions for a successful operation are not present, they withdraw before reaching the final phase of the ambush. This withdrawal occurs prior to the execution of the concrete operational act (Kosovo Police, Lesson No. 3, 2015:10).

Action: Action represents the final element of the ambush and occurs once the attackers are convinced that the conditions are favorable and that the assault must be executed. Attackers are often characterized by a high degree of emotional control and are prepared to wait for extended periods to complete their mission. However, empirical evidence indicates that prolonged waiting frequently increases stress levels and psychological pressure, which can ultimately lead to operational failure. Therefore, the effectiveness of an assassination is not determined by a fixed time frame. Nevertheless, operational advantage is generally achieved when the VIP's movement is slow or temporarily stationary, when protective coverage is inadequate, and when precise timing is applied in approaching the target. The combination of these factors significantly increases the likelihood of a successful attack.

In addition to the main elements of an ambush, there are also general elements of attacks against VIPs that pose serious threats to public officials, institutions, and other protected persons. These general elements include:

- **Preliminary planning:** Observation and analysis of the target's routines and movement patterns.
- **Selection of timing:** Exploitation of predictable situations, without reference to operational specifics.
- **Element of surprise:** Intention to catch the target unprepared and reduce reaction time.
- **Security vulnerabilities:** Insufficient protection measures or lack of coordination among security personnel.
- **Environmental factors:** Physical spaces that restrict movement, reaction, or escape.

- Disinformation: The use of distraction or the deliberate creation of confusion to facilitate the attack.

7.2. Planning the Attack Objectives

The planning of attack objectives represents a fundamental stage in deliberate criminal or terrorist actions. According to Clarke and Cornish, offenders engage in rational decision-making processes in which they define objectives, assess risks, select targets, and choose appropriate methods in order to maximize effectiveness and minimize exposure (Clarke & Cornish, 2001:23–24).

This planning phase typically includes intelligence gathering, weapon selection, identification of vulnerable locations, and preparation of escape routes. Understanding these processes is essential for security and close protection professionals, as it enables them to anticipate potential threats and implement proactive countermeasures aimed at disrupting planned attacks.

As noted earlier, attacks are rarely executed hastily or randomly. Instead, attackers generally rely on carefully developed and, in many cases, highly sophisticated tactics to achieve their objectives. Among the oldest and most effective of these tactics is the ambush, which has historically remained a persistent and serious concern for protective teams.

In this context, the primary purpose of planning and clearly defining attack objectives is to:

- Capture/Kill/Harass, etc.;
- Gather information about the targeted person;
- Determine the “kill zone”;
- Determine the weapons to be used;
- Select the individuals who will carry out the attack, while others handle security, support, etc.;
- Plan the methods and escape routes.

Given the high level of risk faced by persons of special importance, which may be further exacerbated by the deliberate planning of potential attackers, it is imperative that operators responsible for VIP security maintain heightened vigilance. In addition, the coordinated engagement of all relevant security mechanisms, including intelligence services, is crucial for the prevention of both the planning and execution of attacks by various criminal entities (Kosovo Police, Lesson #4, 2022:11).

8. CONCLUSION

Securing domestic and international personalities is a process that requires great attention and a high level of professional preparation. When it comes to protecting personalities, the level of risk must first be considered so that measures can be taken according to the risk level. Protection of very important persons is carried out by protective operators who must possess high intelligence and advanced training. Planning and protection are the two most important aspects of the protective team. The protective team, which forms the close circle around the protected person, must know the personality's exact schedule. During escorting, the team must continuously observe the surroundings, be aware of the public near the VIP, and plan their activities based on this information.

Practical experience has shown that the most effective protection occurs when intelligence services have sufficient information about the location the VIP will visit or regarding any potential threats. The information possessed by the intelligence team must be given to the person responsible for the protective team so that it can be used to implement the operational plan, such as changing the personality's scheduled agenda or canceling all meetings if it is verified that the risk may be unavoidable.

It must always be kept in mind that during escorting, without timely and accurate information, the security and protection of the personality are significantly jeopardized. Experience has shown that when the protective team does not have information regarding a potential threat, risk elimination depends entirely on the professional preparation of the team's operators. In these cases, vigilance is paramount, as the operators must be fully aware that their eyes must detect anything suspicious around them and the person under protection. It must always be taken into consideration that 100% or absolute security has not yet been provided by any close protection system. However, since the protective team is primarily responsible for the lives of VIPs, they are legally obliged to take all measures to ensure the persons under protection are provided with security according to the law and existing regulations.

Since the duties and responsibilities of close protection operators are specific and carry great weight, two factors that can make their work more effective are: cooperation with all intelligence services and having timely information, as well as their special and continuous training with the full arsenal they possess according to their tasks and responsibilities.

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